

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1845	Bernhard Ludwig Suphan	1866	1866	1910		German philologist, known for his historical-critical edition of the complete works of Johann Gottfried Herder (33 volumes)	1845-1911
1845	Mary Frere	1866	No	1910	w	British English ethnologist and author of works regarding India	1845-1911
1845	Carl Sachau	1867	1867	1915		German Orientalist	1845-1930
1845	Archibald Sayce	1868		1919		British Assyriologist and linguist	1845-1933
1845	Otto Hense	1868	1868	1909		German classical philologist known for his investigations of Sophocles and the anthologist Stobaeus	1845-1931
1845	Jan Baudouin de Courtenay	1870	1870	1929		Polish linguist and Slavist	1845-1929
1845	Wilhelm von Bode	1870	1870	1920		German art historian and museum curator	1845-1929
1845	Henry Sweet	1871		1912		British English philologist, phonetician and grammarian	1845-1912
1845	Richard Paul Wülker	1872	1872	1910		German Anglist	1845-1910
1845	Henry Bradley	1877		1923		British philologist and lexicographer	1845-1923
1845	Lucy Myers Wright Mitchell	1883		1888	w	American writer, historian, and expert on ancient art	1845-1888
1846	William Robertson Smith	1868		1894		British Scottish orientalist, Old Testament scholar, professor of divinity, and minister of the Free Church of Scotland.	1846-1894
1846	Hermann Paul	1868	1870	1910		German linguist and lexicographer	1846-1921
1846	Friedrich Carl Andreas	1868	1868	1930		German orientalist	1846-1930
1846	Samuel Rolles Driver	1869		1914		British English divine and Hebrew scholar	1846-1914
1846	Ernst Kuhn	1869	1869	1917		German Indologist and Indo-Europeanist	1846-1920
1846	Samuel Landauer	1872	1872	1918		German Jewish orientalist and librarian	1846-1937
1846	George Gwilliam	1874	1874	1913		British English Aramaicist and Hebraist	1846-1913
1846	Friedrich Eduard König	1874	1879	1926		German Lutheran divine and Semitic scholar	1846-1936
1846	Karl Verner	1874		1896		Danish linguist	1846-1896
1846	Wilhelm Herrmann	1875	1875	1916		German Lutheran theologian	1846-1922
1846	Caspar René Gregory	1876	1876	1914		American-German theologian	1846-1917
1846	Charles Ernest Fay	1877	No	1922		American linguist	1846-1931
1846	Jean-Pierre Roussetot	1891		1924		French priest who was an important phonetician and dialectologist	1846-1924

1846	Hermine Hartleben	1894	No	1915	w	German Egyptologist, biographer of Jean-François Champollion	1846-1919
1847	Hermann Osthoff	1869	1869	1900		German linguist	1847-1909
1847	Ferdinand Vetter	1872	1872	1910		Swiss Germanist and medievalist	1847-1924
1847	Ōtsuki Fumihiko	1872	No	1915		Japanese lexicographer, linguist, and historian	1847-1928
1847	Karl Penka	1874		1912		Austrian philologist and anthropologist	1847-1912
1847	Seweryn Obst	1875	No	1910		Ukrainian-Polish painter, illustrator and ethnographer	1847-1917
1847	Fedir Vovk	1883	1900	1918		Ukrainian anthropologist-archaeologist, the curator of the Alexander III Museum in St. Petersburg	1847-1918
1847	Joseph Loth	1883		1930		French linguist and historian who specialised in the study of Celtic languages	1847-1934
1847	Jervoise Athelstane Baines	1892	No	1910		British administrator in the Indian Civil Service during the period of the British Raj	1847-1925
1847	Sara Yorke Stevenson	1892	No	1920	w	American archaeologist specializing in Egyptology, one of the founders of the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology, suffragist and women's rights activist	1847-1921
1848	Gregorios Bernardakis	1867		1923		Greek philologist, palaeographer	1848-1925
1848	Elias von Steinmeyer	1869	1869	1913		German philologist	1848-1922
1848	Hermann Alexander Diels	1870	1870	1920		German classical scholar	1848-1922
1848	Ulrich von Wilamowitz-Moellendorff	1870	1870	1927		German classical philologist	1848-1931
1848	Richard Meister	1871	1871	1910		German classical scholar and linguist	1848-1912
1848	Anton Emanuel Schönbach	1871	1871	1911		Austrian Germanist, cultural and literary scholar	1848-1911
1848	Michael Deffner	1871	1871	1910		German classical philologist and linguist, known for his studies exploring the Tsakonian language	1848-1934
1848	Hermann Suchier	1871	1871	1914		German Romance philologist of Huguenot ancestry	1848-1914
1848	Richard Carl Meister	1872	1872	1910		German classical scholar and linguist	1848-1912
1848	Heinrich Hübschmann	1872		1908		German philologist	1848-1908
1848	Филипп Фортунатов	1875		1914		Russian linguist	1848-1914
1848	Kazimieras Jaunius	1879		1906		Lithuanian Catholic priest and linguist	1848-1908
1848	Théophile Homolle	1879	1887	1923		French archaeologist and classical philologist	1848-1925
1848	Edward Charles Stirling	1880	1880	1913		Australian anthropologist and the first professor of physiology at the University of Adelaide	1848-1919
1848	Charles Bémont	1884	1884	1939		French scholar	1848-1939

1848	William Crooke	1897	1919	1923	British orientalist and a key figure in the study and documentation of Anglo-Indian folklore	1848-1923
1849	Louis Havet	1867	1880	1925	French Latinist and Hellenist, an expert on classical Greek and Latin poetry	1849-1925
1849	Karl Brugmann	1871	1871	1919	German linguist (Indo-European linguistics)	1849-1919
1849	Italo Pizzi	1872		1920	Italian academic and scholar of Persian language and literature (establish the academic field of Persian language and literature in Italy)	1849-1920
1849	Georg Goetz	1873	1873	1923	German classical philologist	1849-1932
1849	Adolf Kaegi	1875	1875	1914	Swiss Indologist and Greekist	1849-1923
1849	William Gardner Hale	1876	1876	1920	American classical scholar	1849-1928
1849	Adolf Birch-Hirschfeld	1877	1877	1914	German medievalist and Romance scholar	1849-1917
1849	Hermann Guthe	1877	1877	1921	German Semitic scholar	1849-1936
1849	Constantin Dimitrescu-Iași	1877	1877	1919	Romanian philosopher, sociologist and pedagogue	1849-1923
1849	Otto Stoll	1877	1877	1919	Swiss linguist and ethnologist	1849-1922
1849	Henri Cordier	1878		1925	French linguist, historian, ethnographer, author, editor and Orientalist	1849-1925
1849	George Bird Grinnell	1880	1880	1927	American anthropologist, historian, naturalist, and write	1849-1938
1849	Matilda Coxe Stevenson	1881	No	1910 w	American ethnologist, geologist, and explorer	1849-1915
1849	Eduard Seler	1887	1887	1922	German anthropologist, ethnohistorian, linguist, epigrapher, academic and Americanist scholar, who made extensive contributions in these fields towards the study of pre-Columbian era cultures in the Americas	1849-1922
1849	Ernst von Mohl	1889		1911	German classical philologist and professor	1849-1929
1849	Walter Frederic Adeney	1893		1913	British English Congregationalist minister, theologian, and biblical scholar	1849-1920